

The owner of a \$7.5 million vintage car collection, [George Nader](#) is born in 1960 in New York. This car enthusiast possesses more than 70 rare eclectic cars, which he has fully restored with his own hands. Nader's collection of the finest and most sought vintage cars, such as Carroll Shelby Cobra, Lamborghini Miura, Ferrari F40, Mercedes-Benz 300 SL Gullwing, Porsche RS o Turbo S, McLaren P1, has been presented on many car exhibitions around the world.

As [a mechanic engineer by profession](#), with a Bachelor's degree from the Civil Engineering and Engineering Mechanics Department of the University of New York, Nader founded Nader's Car-Recycling and Repairing. Firstly, he was working in his garage. Later he expanded his business to a new location.

When his business started flourishing, he was able to fulfill his childhood dream of buying a Porsche. Nader bought a 1965 Porsche 356 Speedster, which he fully restored. This was the first car in his collection.